

*The practical advantages of the integrative model in
patient health care*

Paulo Nuno Martins

In medical practice, the biomedical model is the most used model in the treatment of patients, according to the Cartesian perspective, which defends the duality of the mind (domain of philosophy and religion) and the body (domain of science), where the body is treated as a “machine”. In this regard, there are some research works that address this subject, through the intersection of science and spirituality [1]. In the beginning of the 20th century, with the appearance of quantum physics (with the study of particle physics) and psychology (with the study of the mind), the Cartesian perspective was challenged by the works of Pauli and Jung [2], due to the deepening study of the mind-body relationship, which contributed to the appearance of the biopsychosocial model [3].

In fact, medical sciences have faced clinical situations in which the biomedical model does not respond satisfactorily to certain clinical events, as it is necessary to take into account other dimensions of the human being, namely in near death experience (NDE) and out of body experience (OBE) [4]. For example, in NDE and OBE, some patients have reported the experiences of “entering a tunnel of light that leads them to meet (sometimes) with relatives who have already left” through the phenomenon of “synchronicity”, and the justification goes beyond of pathologies and medication effects (which promote hallucinations) defended by the biomedical model. On the contrary, there is a set of phenomena, with several levels of complexity, that go far beyond this restrictive perspective. In these situations, on the “edge of knowledge”, the integrative model is the one that best suits this type of occurrences because it considers the various dimensions of the patient: body-mind-soul.

In the psychological area, it is important to take note of the work carried out by the psychologist Carl Jung [5], who made the connection between the psychological and spiritual

sides of the human being through the concept of “archetype” within the scope of psychotherapy. This tool allows the self-awareness of “patterns” during the healing process. Carl Jung also proposed several psychological types of the individuals according to their behavior, presenting some analogies with the mind-body characteristics proposed by Ayurveda, called “doshas” (vata, pitta, kapha).

Regarding the care of the patient’s psychological dimension, some studies on this field [6] indicate that alongside the treatment of patients with covid-19, it is also important to pay attention to the psychological state of people who have lost their jobs, favoring depression states, as well as the burnout situations suffered by health professionals due to the excessive hours of work combating the pandemic. These situations also require some health care, according to the integrative perspective.

Furthermore, of all the dimensions in humans, the spiritual dimension is the strongest and exerts the biggest impact on the other dimensions of the human being, as suggested by the transcendental experiences lived by Sister Bernardette Moriau and the philosopher Jiddu Krishnamurti, who came from very different cultures [7]. In fact, the study of the spiritual dimension of the human being is worth mentioning, through the so-called “spontaneous cures”, such as the recent case of Sister Bernardette Moriau, who after going on pilgrimage to the Lourdes Sanctuary, was cured of her disease called “cauda equine syndrome”. The Lourdes Medical Bureau (BCM, Bureau des Constatations Médicales) and International Medical Committee of Lourdes (CMIL, Comité Médical International de Lourdes), through the current president, Prof. Dr. Alessandro de Franciscis, declared this clinical situation as “unexplained according to the current medical knowledge” after applying the “Lambertini criteria”. After this procedure, a canonical process validated this “spontaneous cure” as “miraculous”. Thus, some studies seeking a new approach to these situations through the intersection of the assumptions of quantum physics, transpersonal psychology and Indian philosophies have emerged. In this perspective, it is argued that the “quantum intricacy” between the patient and the healing entity, according to Assagioli’s “Egg Diagram” and the assumptions of the Indian philosophies of “awakening the kundalini with the opening of chakras”, may justify such occurrences.

In this regard, since the 1970s, the integrative model has been proposed by several physicians, such as Andrew Weil and Paulo de Lima, in the West, and Ram Vishwakarma, in the East, among others, in order to treat not only the physical and biological side, but also the psychological and spiritual side of the patient. Thus, the integrative model arose from the need to carry out the diagnosis and treatment of the patient, in a more comprehensive and global way. In historical terms, integrative medicine emerged with the aim of linking Eastern history and philosophy (through the assumptions of Ayurveda and traditional Chinese medicine) with Western history and philosophy, while considering the spiritual dimension of the human

being [8].

It is also important to mention the work carried out by the scientists Humberto Maturana and Francisco Varela who show that biological systems, such as the human beings, are self-poietic and self-conscious and this self-perception determines the structure of the entire self-organization network, in which the biological system is interconnected and interdependent [9]. For example, in the perspective of the biomedical model, the nervous, endocrine and immune systems are separate entities, whereas in the integrative perspective, these systems are interconnected and influence each other, and so they may contribute to the occurrences of extraordinary cures in certain clinical situations, where the internal organs could be “tuned” by these systems, through the so-called “endogenous recovery system” [10].

So, a brain-mind model proposed by the physician Stuart Hameroff and the mathematician Roger Penrose emerged. They proposed a model with a “quantum component of the mind” (located in tubulins), responsible for altering the patient’s behavior “patterns”, and a “classic component of the mind” (located in the dendritic membranes), responsible for the conditioned behavior of the person in daily life [11]. In summary, there are several clinical situations where the integrative model has advantages in patient health care because it considers a transdisciplinary perspective of reality, where the various levels of internal perception of the “Subject” are interconnected with the different levels of Reality of the “Object”, thus linking all dimensions of the person (body-mind-spirit), as studied in psychoneuroimmunology [12].

References

1. Martins P. (2009). *A Mecânica Quântica e o pensamento de Amit Goswami*. Tese de doutoramento em História e Filosofia da Ciência. Universidade Nova de Lisboa. (PhD Thesis in History and Philosophy of Science) FCT.UNL Publishers. URI: <http://hdl.handle.net/10362/1939> [It should be complemented with the article Martins P. (2018). Descartes and the paradigm of Western medicine: An essay. *International Journal of Recent Advances in Science and Technology*, 5(3):32-34].
2. Jung C., Pauli W. (1955). *The Nature and Interpretation of the Psyche*. New York, NY: Pantheon Books.
3. de Marco M. (2006). From the biomedical to the biopsychosocial model: a project of permanent education. *Revista Brasileira de Educação Médica*, 30(1): 60-72.
4. Martins P. (2019). *Ciência e a teoria da «vida após a morte»: Algumas considerações*

- sobre a filosofia da ética. *Revista Consciências* 6, Universidade Fernando Pessoa, 67-80. URI:<http://hdl.handle.net/10284/7720>.
5. Jung C. (2011). *Obra Completa de C.G. Jung*. Petrópolis, RJ: Editora Vozes.
 6. Several authors (2021). *2020 R&B Research Report: COVID-19*. ATLAS Publishing.
 7. Martins P. (2020). A perspective on the “spontaneous” cures associated with the Sacred: A historical case. *International Journal of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education*, 7(5):35-40 [it should be complemented with the article Martins P. (2021). As filosofias da Índia e a “cura” espontânea da Irmã Bernardette Moriau: Algumas perspectivas. *Revista Consciências* 7, Universidade Fernando Pessoa (accepted for publication)].
 8. Martins P. (2020). A Model of Integrative Medicine for Health Care in Contemporary Society. *Biomedical Journal of Scientific&Technical Research*, 28(2): 21461-21464.
 9. Capra F. (1996). *The Web of Life*. New York, NY: Simon and Schuster.
 10. Hirshberg C., Barasch M. (1995). *Remarkable Recovery: What Extraordinary Healing Tell Us About Getting Well and Staying Well*. Nova York, NY: Riverhead Hardcover.
 11. Hameroff S., Penrose R. (1996). Orchestrated reduction of quantum coherence in brain microtubules – a model for consciousness. *Toward a Science of Consciousness: contributions from the 1994 Tucson Conference*, In: Hameroff S., Kaszniak A., Scott A. (eds.). Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
 12. Martins P. (2019). Being Transdisciplinary in Human Sciences: The usefulness of integrative medicine in contemporary society. *Being Transdisciplinary*, In: Nicolescu B., Yeh R., Ertas A. (eds.), ATLAS Publishing, 5:39-47.